

NOTES

Formation Constants of Pr(III), Y(III) and Dy(III) Complexes of Some Schiff bases of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde.

A Potentiometric Study

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POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on complexes of Pr^{3+} , Y^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with a series of structurally similar schiff bases so selected as to vary the ligand basicity due to substituents at one of the coordinating sites. Proton association constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the ligands and formation constants ($\log K$) of their 1 : 1 metal complexes have been determined at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at an ionic strength of 0.1 M in 75 : 25 per cent (v/v) dioxan : water medium by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹. The values of $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated from the titration data which in turn were used to compute the $\log K$ values of the metal complexes by the half integral method.

For evaluating the similarity in bonding of proton as well as of metal ion to ligand molecule the pK versus $\log K$ relation was examined.

Experimental

Following schiff bases were synthesised and their purity was ascertained by determining melting points and by carrying out T.L.C. and elemental analyses.

Ligand	Observed m.p. °C	Literature m.p. °C
A 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene- α -naphthylamine	178	178 ^a
B 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-diethylaniline	77	—
C 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-ortho-methylaniline	137	138 ^b
D 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-ortho-fluoroaniline	104	—
E 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-ortho-bromoaniline	150	150 ^a

Experimental details and the computational methods were the same as reported in our earlier communication⁵.

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ions

during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the total number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one. Due to protonation of the imine nitrogen in strongly acidic medium, in the case of A, B & C ligands, the ligand titration curve indicated higher B values as compared to the acid titration curve for the same addition of alkali.

The stability constants of the selected metals with the different organic ligands have been tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Cation	Constant	$\mu = 0.1M$				
		Ligand				
		A	B	C	D	E
H^+	$\log K_1^H$	10.15	9.90	10.85	9.34	9.42
	$\log K_2^H$	2.40	2.48	2.80	—	—
Pr^{3+}	$\log K_1$	7.15	6.95	7.87	6.17	6.05
Y^{3+}	$\log K_1$	7.70	7.40	8.15	7.30	6.60
Dy^{3+}	$\log K_1$	8.70	7.43	8.33	6.85	6.95

The $\log K$ versus pK plots (Fig. 1) follow a linear relationship in a rather approximate manner.

Fig. 1 Plots of $\log k_1$ versus pK_1

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Metal Complexes of N-Phenyl-N'-p-Bromophenyl Thiourea

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SEVERAL complexes of thioureas have been reported by various workers¹⁻⁶. Very few references⁷⁻¹⁰ have been found with regard to the complexes of unsymmetrical thioureas. Further, certain thiourea derivatives have been found to have analytical¹¹⁻¹³ and biological importance¹⁴⁻¹⁶. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to investigate the metal complexes of N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea.

Preparation of Metal complexes :

Ethanolic solution of copper and nickel chloride, bromide, iodide, acetate and nitrate were treated with hot ethanolic solution of N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 ratio

separately and solution refluxed for 50 minutes. The complexes were filtered, washed with a little of ethanol, dry chloroform and dried in vacuo. Their melting points, elemental analysis and magnetic moments are listed in Table 1.

Metal and sulphur in the complexes were estimated by a standard methods. A Coleman Analyser was used for the estimation of nitrogen. Conductance was measured in M/100 dioxane solution using "Toshniwal Conductivity bridge". Infrared spectra in Nujol mulls were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer (Model-720). The magnetic susceptibility was determined by a Faraday Cahn Electrobalance (Model-7550) using mercuric tetrathio-cyanato cobaltate(II) as the standard and using the gram susceptibility values¹⁷. Diamagnetic correction was applied by the use of Pascal's constants.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported in the present investigation are of the compositions [Cu L X], [Cu L₂ X], [Cu L₃ X] and [Ni L₂ X₂] where X = Cl, Br, I and L = N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea. All these complexes are non-electrolytes and the Δ_M values in dioxane solution (M/1000) are very very low. The [Cu L X], [Cu L₂ X], [Cu L₃ X] and [Ni L₂ X₂] complexes are diamagnetic and show sp, sp², sp³ and dsp² types of hybridization.

The infrared spectra of all the complexes of thiourea(L) follow a general pattern and detailed discussion have been recorded. The compounds containing a thioamide moiety have been studied by several workers and it has been suggested that all such compounds give rise to four thioamide bands¹⁸⁻²¹ in their infrared spectra. The four thioamide bands are observed in ligand(L) at 1540, 1250, 1020 and 775 cm⁻¹. The NH absorption bands in the spectrum of thiourea(L) are not shifted to lower wave number on the formation of the metal thiourea complexes indicating that the nitrogen to metal bonds are absent. The sharp band is not observed at 3200 cm⁻¹, is undoubtedly assigned to

TABLE 1—METAL COMPLEXES OF N-PHENYL-N'-p-BROMOPHENYL THIOUREA

Sl. No.	Compound	M.P. (°C)	%M		%N		%S	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	CuL ₂ NO ₃	195	6.98	6.07	9.21	9.36	9.46	9.17
2.	CuLOAc	>250	14.47	14.79	6.20	6.51	7.73	7.44
3.	CuLCl	173	15.53	15.64	6.58	6.89	8.18	7.88
4.	CuL ₂ Cl	141	8.61	8.91	7.63	7.85	9.18	8.97
5.	CuL ₂ Br	98	8.24	8.98	7.08	7.39	8.69	8.44
6.	CuL ₂ I	200	7.59	7.89	6.66	6.96	8.26	7.95
7.	CuL ₂ Cl	198	6.01	6.22	8.01	8.23	9.66	9.41
8.	NiL ₂ Cl ₂	125	7.58	7.89	7.81	7.52	8.46	8.60
9.	NiL ₂ Br ₂	143	6.76	7.05	7.02	6.72	7.53	7.68
10.	NiL ₂ I ₂	130	6.01	6.33	6.34	6.04	6.88	6.91